

ELECTRONIC BANKING MECHANISMS AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN A CASHLESS POLICY ERA: STUDY OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS.

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Abstract: *The Nigeria cashless policy has been saddled with numerous challenges experienced by bank's customers, employees and even owners. This is as a result of inefficient electronic banking method. Many deposit money banks in Nigeria have tried some measures to improve their electronic banking services, yet the cashless policy is still a mirage to many Nigerians. The aim of this study is to identify how to utilize electronic banking methods on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks. To realize this, primary data was obtained from employees of selected Deposit Money Bank Branches in FCT Abuja. Result of data analysis reveals that a significant relationship exists between cashless policy implementation and electronic banking tools including Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Electronic Fund transfer, Mobile Banking, and Point of Sale (POS) machines. Based on the findings, the study recommends that for electronic banking to be effective and realize its needed objectives, all Deposit Money Banks should: ensure a 24/7 uninterrupted internet services for all their operations to encourage mobile banking; adequately train and periodically retrain its personnel to ease and encourage customers' patronage for electronic money transfer; provide Automated Teller Machines (ATM) in all parts of the country to expand customers' access to the machines; and also provide Point of Sale machines to customers at zero-cost to encourage use of the machines.*

Introduction

'A Bank is a financial institution that accepts deposits and channels the money into lending activities. Deposit Money Bank is a financial institution that accepts demand deposits and provides loans and other financial services to the public. In Nigeria, Deposit Money Banks

represent the backbone of the banking system through their products to customers. These products are facilitated by electronic banking system. Electronic banking system affects all processes associated with modern day banking. Modern day banking activities involves routine daily banking activities such as accepting

deposits and granting or affecting withdrawals through physical means or the automated machines, fund transfers and electronic mobile banking, preparing payroll and order entry, to other strategic activities such as interbank transactions. The importance of electronic banking system to the commercial banking sector in Nigeria is more tasking in a cashless policy implementation era. This is because, a cashless policy in an economy requires the application of electronic banking tools by banks and other financial institutions for the goals and objectives of the policy to be achieved.

Cashless Policy is a monetary instrument developed by the Central Bank of Nigeria that is aimed at reducing the amount of currency in circulation, and to encourage the electronic method of financial and business transactions (Ogeide, 2018). Cashless policy represents a situation where payments for business and financial transactions are made and recorded without money being physically exchanged by the parties involved in the transactions. The Central Bank of Nigeria have numerous reasons to belief that the implementation of the cashless policy will reasonably reduce the amount of physical cash in circulation, and at the same time encourage the use of electronic platforms for executing transactions that involve payments for goods and services and to overcome the risks associated with carrying large amount of cash around such as theft, armed robbery and kidnapping.

Statement of the Problem

Unfortunately, the implementation of the cashless policy in Nigeria coincided with redesigning of the Nigeria currency. This further

exposed the technological weakness of Nigeria banking system. Every Nigerian now have reasons to belief that a lot still need to be done to attract the confidence and trust of the channels for electronic banking which is aimed at aiding cashless banking transactions. This belief is as a result of numerous challenges experienced by bank's customers, employees and even owners. Some of these challenges associated with the use and effective and efficient implementation of the cashless policy include: lack of understanding and proper guidance on the use and implementation of the cashless policy tools, lack of technical skills by both customers and employees, unwillingness of the populace to embrace the policy, lack of technical facilities to make the policy work smoothly, incessant technical hitches such as network problem and unavailability of data, high charges, delays and stress in retrieving unpaid debts, vulnerability of the policy to fraudulent activities, and rude behavior of most bank personnel (Agu & Agu, 2020). Many deposit money banks in Nigeria have tried some measures to improve their electronic banking services, yet the cashless policy is still a mirage to many Nigerians. This therefore calls for the need to identify how to utilize electronic banking mechanisms such as the automatic teller machines (ATM), Internet or electronic banking, electronic fund transfers and Point of Sale (POS) to enable the banks achieve customer's patronage.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to identify how to utilize electronic banking methods on the implementation of cashless policy by

Deposit Money Banks. Other specific objectives include to:

- i. ascertain the impact of Automated Teller Machines (ATM) on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks;
- ii. identify the effect of electronic fund transfer on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks;
- iii. discover the effect of mobile banking on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks; and
- iv. examine the effect of Point of Sale (POS) operations on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

Research Hypotheses

HO₁ = Automated Teller Machines (ATM) has no effect on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

HO₂ == Electronic fund transfer does not affect the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

HO₃ == Mobile Banking has no significant impact on the implementation of cashless policy by Zenith Bank.

HO₄ == Point of Sale (POS) operations does not significantly affect the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

Methodology

To realize the aim and objectives of this study, this study utilized the applied research design. This is because the research focused on the collection of information about various aspects of situation and problems associated with cashless policy implementation. For this study, primary data was obtained with questionnaire distributed through convenient sampling to 187 respondents statistically selected from 350

employees of selected Deposit Money Bank Branches in FCT Abuja. Data collected from the field were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, while the hypotheses postulated were tested using the Regression analysis executed through SPSS version 26.0. Also, secondary data for the study was realized through a review of literatures relevant to this study. Literature review was achieved through conceptual review, theoretical review, and empirical review.

Conceptual Review and Framework

Concept of Electronic Banking

Electronic Banking refers to 'the technology which consists of electronic devices and associated human interactive materials that enable the Banks to employ them for a wide range of banking services. Simply put, electronic banking is the use of electronic and technological devices in the transfer and use of communication of messages in banking transactions. Electronic banking has discouraged the use of physical methods of transactions and communication such as writing on paper and walls, documentation through physical objects such as files and papers and also communication through paper. These commercial banking products are facilitated by electronic banking. Electronic banking involves how to utilize electronic banking mechanisms such as the automatic teller machines (ATM), Internet or electronic banking, electronic fund transfers and Point of Sale (POS) to enable the banks achieve customer's patronage.

Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

Automated Teller Machines (ATM) are electronically controlled machines or computer-controlled devices created and positioned at strategic and accessible points to dispense cash, accept deposits and provide some other financial information services to customers on 24hours basis. Its operations are enabled after a computerized identification of the customers' personalized information. The aim of Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) is to provide customers cash withdrawals and cash deposits, electronic money transfers within the country to other banks and checking of balance. A second major advantage of the use of Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) is that it reduces the cost of having more personnel to attend to customers physically. This is because Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) are situated not only inside bank premises, but also in strategic or business-oriented positions such as shopping centers, shopping malls, Airports, grocery stores, petrol and gas stations, educational institutions, restaurants, local or community markets and other places where large crowd of persons are experienced.

Electronic Fund Transfer

This is a situation where customers enter the banking hall, fill fund transfer documents and transfer funds from their accounts to other accounts. Fund transfer is a situation where customers hand over their fund transfer request documents to the bank employee in the banking hall who would electronically execute the transfers as requested by the customer. The major disadvantages to these methods of fund and financial transactions include that: the customer must be physically present in the Bank

to fill the necessary forms; the presence of the bank employee is necessary to receive the transfer request from the customers; it requires documentation and confirmation by the bank employees before the request is executed; and there must be internet connectivity for it to be executed. The major advantages associated with fund transfer include that: it is most secured because the customer is not prone to exposing his or her bank details to persons other than the bank personnel attending to him or her; the security of the customer's fund is guaranteed since there is no threat of customers account being debited without the execution of the fund transfer request; and there is less or no threat of internet availability.

Mobile Banking

This is the banking system where customers carryout their banking transactions through the aid of information and communication technology without physically coming to the banking hall. The practice of mobile or online banking has made banking transactions more convenient to customers. This is because through mobile or online banking, customers can carry out banking transactions such as account balance, pay bills online, transfer funds, study recent transactions and block ATM cards if fraud is suspected. Most importantly, mobile or online banking is highly dependent on availability of an internet or data connection to mobile devices. This means that the customer must have an internet compliant device such as smart phone or laptop to be able to utilize this method of banking. The major advantage is that the customer does not need to come to the bank to execute bank transactions; it is a 24 hours

service that enables customers to execute transaction such as pay for purchase and make online payments without barriers. The major disadvantages include that: it is exposed to fraud as customers' accounts are frequently hacked; there is the problem of internet availability; there is the problem of power supply especially for customers who always experience low battery of their devices; it is costly because the associated charges for both the banks and customers are high; and there is also the issue of debit reversal against customer thereby attracting much complaints from customers.

Point of Sale (POS) Terminal Device

Point of Sale Terminal is an electronic device used to process electronic card payments at retail locations. "A Point of Sale (POS) terminal is used to execute financial transactions such as: read the information of a customer's credit or debit card; checks if the funds in the customer's bank account are sufficient; transfers funds from the customer's account to the seller's account; provide cash for the customer upon demand; and records transactions and prints receipts for the transactions. Point of Sale (POS) Terminal comprise of a combination of soft and hardware that allows retail locations to accept card payments without updating their cash registers to read cards directly. "This is

because the cost of installing a Point of Sale (POS) terminal varies with the size of the business and the terms from the suppliers. Small merchants may have to pay rent for the terminal as well as pay an additional per-transaction fee.

Cashless Policy

Cashless Policy is a monetary instrument developed by the Central Bank of Nigeria that is aimed at reducing the amount of currency in circulation, and to encourage the electronic method of financial and business transactions (Ogeide, 2018). Cashless policy represents a situation where payments for business and financial transactions are made and recorded without money being physically exchanged by the parties involved in the transactions. The Central Bank of Nigeria have numerous reasons to belief that the implementation of the cashless policy will reasonably reduce the amount of physical cash in circulation, and at the same time encourage the use of electronic platforms for executing transactions that involve payments for goods and services. The cashless policy as a monetary policy in Nigeria bought the use of electronic banking tools such as ATM, NEFT, POS, NIP, USSD, and other forms of mobile banking such as electronic fund transfers and cheque (Ejiobih, 2019).

Conceptual Review

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 2.1 showing Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's effort, 2023.

Theoretical Review and Framework Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory

This theory was originally propounded by Denning in 2004. This theory is made up of three major components which include: Innovation, Diffusion and Adoption. In the theory Denning, 2004 defined an Innovation 'as an idea, practice or object that is perceived to be new by a person adopting the entity; Diffusion means communicating or spreading of the news of the innovation to the group or individual for

which it is intended, while Adoption is the commitment to and continued use of the innovation'. Refining this theory, Rogers, 1995 postulates that "diffusion of innovation occur when potential users of the innovation become aware of the innovation, judge its relative value and make a decision based on their judgment that leads to implementing or rejecting the innovation, and seek confirmation of the adoption or rejection decision".

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

This theory was propounded by Wemerfelt in 1984. The theory proposes that a firm's performance is determined by the resources it owns. Applying this theory to the use of electronic banking, it is believed that electronic banking is an organizational resource that can enhance organizational capabilities and eventually lead to higher performance of the organization. Other followers of the theory state that organizational resources that can create advantage must have the following attributes: "valuable (this means that the resource can enable a firm to conceive or implement strategies that can improve its efficiency or effectiveness); rare (this means that the resources should not be possessed by a large number of competing firms); imperfectly imitable (this means that the resources should not be easily imitated due to unique historical conditions, causally ambiguous, or social complex); and non-substitutable (this means that the resource should not be easily replaced by other substitutes)".

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework or underpinning theory for this study is the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory. This theory was originally propounded by Denning in 2004. The reason is because of the implication of this theory. The implication of this theory is that there is need to develop new ways to execute banking and financial transactions or activities. This way is the electronic banking and its utilization in the banking industry.

Empirical Review

Challenges of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) usage and fraud occurrences in Nigeria: A case

study of selected banks in Minna Metropolis, was executed by Adepoju, 2023. This study is empirical research aimed at analyzing the case of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) usage and fraud occurrences within some banks in Minna and the relevant solutions. The study employed a case study of three banks in Minna to find out how frauds are perpetrated with the use of ATM card. The population of the study comprises of 150 ATM cards users of three banks in Minna namely Intercontinental Bank, Guaranty Trust Banks, and United bank of Africa (UBA). A structured questionnaire was employed as the research instrument. The data obtained was analyzed using the percentage method. The major findings include: the major victims of ATM fraud are male who are within the age range of 21-25 years most of whom are students who are not aware of any incidence of ATM fraud; the location of the ATM points; a major form of ATM fraud is pin theft; ATM should be better used in the day time. Based on the findings, the study recommends that commercial banks used device and utilized modern information and communication technology to promote the use of ATM devoid of fraud.

Predicting consumer adoption of Point of Sale (POS) E-payment system in Nigeria using extended technology acceptance model was executed by Okeke, et. al., 2017. The study aimed at predicting consumer adoption of Point of Sale (POS) e-payment system in Nigeria using extended technology acceptance model. The study was based on the responses from 400 respondents in Awka Nigeria obtained through a questionnaire. Data obtained was analyzed

using the structural equation modeling. The major findings from the study include that: perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness positively and significantly impact POS adoption in Nigeria; security impacts PEOU positively and significantly, but insignificantly on Purchase Use (PU); Consumer Awareness (CA) significantly and positively impact PU but the impact on PEOU is not significant. Based on the findings, the study recommends that operators and regulators of POS need to engage the customers more by creating serious awareness on the use of POS for payments instead of cash payments.

Empirical study of the challenges of cashless banking system in Nigeria with respect to cashless banking channels was executed by Kida and Mbanibo, 2018. The aim of this study was to identify how best to over-come the challenges associated with cashless policy in Nigeria. The study adopted exploratory research design. The study population comprised of the management staff and customers of four (4) selected banks in Nigeria. The sample size is 648 and all the banks selected were represented in clusters and administered with the questionnaire as the source of primary data. Data obtained was analyzed using the descriptive frequency analysis and inferential statistics. The major findings include that those factors that affect the prospects of the cashless policy system in Nigeria include machine malfunctions or technical issues, lack of requirements in infrastructural development, infrastructural deficits and religious beliefs. The study recommends that banks should give more priority to ATM based product since most

customers use this channel more than the other channels in the cashless banking system; the banks should also encourage the use of other mobile banking channels so as to encourage the adoption of the cashless banking policy.

The impact of ICT on banks: A case study of Nigeria Banking Industry was executed by Luka, and Frank, 2012. The aim was to ascertain the level of use of ICT infrastructure and their impacts on customer's service which invariably determines growth of banks. A random sampling technique was employed to distribute questionnaire to four hundred (400) customers of four selected banks in port-Harcourt. The data obtained was analyzed through the percentage method. The major findings include: ICT has a positive impact on the productivity of banks employees as perceived by customers; ICT has positive impact on employee's innovation; ICT has improved the quality of service rendered by the bank; and customers are attracted to the bank's services because of perceived value of the bank services. Based on these findings, the study recommends that the bank's needs: to multiply their effort or investment on ICT, human capital and firms restructuring; come up with innovative products that will satisfy customers banking needs at a reduce costs; and bank should ensure they render prompt and efficient service. This study is relevant to our study because it examines the relevance of information and communication technology on the productivity of banks measured though customer satisfaction.

Effect of ICT adoption on competitive performance of banks in an emerging economy: The Nigeria experience was executed by Dalis,

et.al., 2017. This study is a synthesis of empirical facts and the descriptive design was adopted for the execution of this study. The population of the study comprises of 896 staff of Zenith, Diamond, UBA and Guarantee trust banks located in FCT Abuja. A self-administered questionnaire was used to elicit primary data. The data obtained was analyzed with both descriptive and influential statistics while the hypotheses postulated were analyzed with the T-test statistics. The major findings include that: the internet (WEB) transactions have a significant impact on branch expansion of deposit money banks; mobile payment transactions have significant effect on the operations and service delivery of deposit money banks; and ATM transactions have significant influence on profitability levels of deposit money banks. Based on the findings, the study recommends that: banks should

incorporate ICT into their strategic plans for effective performance in payment and delivery system; banks should pay more attention to the use of information and communication technology in all banking operations; and banks should give regular training to bankers to enable them be aware of current innovations in the use of information and communication technology.

Existing Gaps for the Study

The existing gap for this study is that no study has been carried out on the utilization of electronic banking system to realize the implementation of the cashless policy by the Central Bank of Nigeria with the Federal Capital Territory Abuja as case study. The Federal Capital Territory Abuja is the seat of political and economic power of the country with an increasing population. It should therefore be a point of reference for the implementation of the cashless policy by the Central Bank of Nigeria.

Data Analysis and Result

Question One: How long have you served with a Deposit Money Bank?

Table 4.1 Years of Service in Deposit Money Bank

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<5yrs	40	22.2	22.2	22.2
	5-10yrs	50	27.8	27.8	50.0
	11-14yrs	45	25.0	25.0	75.0
	15yrs & above	45	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Source: PSS Output (Based on questionnaires' Data 2023).

Table 4.3 analyzed the respondent's years of working in a Deposit Money Bank. The result indicated that 40 frequencies representing 22.2% are below 5 years; 50 frequencies representing 27.8% are between 5-10 years of service; 45 frequencies representing 25% are between 11-14 years while another 45 frequencies representing 25% had worked with them from 15 years and above. The implication is that the majority of the respondents had served in the bank between 5-10 years with 27.8% of responses.

Question Two: Did you experience the cashless policy implementation era in Deposit Money Bank?

Table 4.2: Experience of Cashless Policy in the Bank

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	170	94.4	94.4	94.4
	No	10	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Source: *SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires" Data 2023).*

The analysis shows that out of the 180 copies of questionnaires retrieved, 170 frequencies representing 94.4% of respondents accepted that they had experienced cashless policy implementation in Deposit Money Bank. However, 10 frequencies representing 5.6% of respondents answered "No" to the experience of the implementation of cashless policy in Deposit Money Bank. The result shows majority of our respondents had experienced cashless policy implementation in Deposit Money Bank; thus, they can answer our questions correctly.

Question Three: From your experience, which of these e-banking methods do your customers utilize most?

Table 4.3: E-Banking Methods Mostly Utilized by Customers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	ATM	60	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Electronic Fund Transfer	30	16.7	16.7	50.0
	Mobile Banking	40	22.2	22.2	72.2
	POS	50	27.8	27.8	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Source: *SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires" Data 2023).*

The analysis revealed that out of the 180 valid questionnaires, response on ATM as the most utilized e-banking method in Deposit Money Banks comprised of 60 frequencies with 33.3%; electronic fund transfer comprised 30 frequencies with 16.7%; mobile banking comprised 40 frequencies with 22.2%, while POS comprised 50 frequencies with 27.8%.

Question four: From your experience, how would you rate the impact of electronic fund transfer transactions on cashless policy implementation of your bank?

Table 4.4: Rating of the Impact of Electronic Fund Transfer on Cashless Policy Implementation by Deposit Money Banks.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Positive	60	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Positive	55	30.6	30.6	63.9
	Moderate	35	19.4	19.4	83.3
	Negative	15	8.3	8.3	91.7
	Very Negative	10	5.6	5.6	97.2
	Not at all	5	2.8	2.8	100.0

Total 180 100.0 100.0

Source: *SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires" Data 2023).*

The result shows that 60 frequencies representing 33.3% of total respondents indicated very positive; 55 frequencies representing 30.6% indicated Positive; 35 frequencies representing 19.4% indicated moderate; 15 frequencies representing 8.3% indicated negative; 10 frequencies representing 5.6% indicated very negative while 5 frequencies representing 2.8% indicated not at all.

Question Five: From your experience, how would you rate the impact of mobile banking transactions on cashless policy implementation in your bank?

Table 4.5: Rating of the Impact of Mobile Banking on Cashless Policy Implementation by Deposit Money Banks.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Positive	60	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Positive	55	30.6	30.6	63.9
	Moderate	35	19.4	19.4	83.3
	Negative	15	8.3	8.3	91.7
	Very Negative	10	5.6	5.6	97.2
	Not at all	5	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Source: *SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires" Data 2023).*

The result shows that 60 frequencies representing 33.3% of total respondents indicated very positive; 55 frequencies representing 30.6% indicated Positive; 35 frequencies representing 19.4% indicated moderate; 15 frequencies representing 8.3% indicated negative; 10 frequencies representing 5.6% indicated very negative while 5 frequencies representing 2.8% indicated not at all.

Question six: From your experience, how would you rate the impact of POS transactions on cashless policy implementation in your bank?

Table 4:6 Rating of the Impact of POS on Cashless Policy Implementation of Deposit Money Banks.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Positive	60	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Positive	55	30.6	30.6	63.9
	Moderate	35	19.4	19.4	83.3
	Negative	15	8.3	8.3	91.7
	Very Negative	10	5.6	5.6	97.2
	Not at all	5	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Source: PSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2023).

The result shows that 60 frequencies representing 33.3% of total respondents indicated very positive; 55 frequencies representing 30.6% indicated Positive; 35 frequencies representing 19.4% indicated moderate; 15 frequencies representing 8.3% indicated negative; 10 frequencies representing 5.6% indicated very negative while 5 frequencies representing 2.8% indicated not at all.

Bivariate Analyses

The bivariate relationship determination in this section was done using Simple Linear Regression in the assessment of the relationship between the dimensions of electronic banking and Cashless Policy Implementation.

The formulae:

$$Y = a + bX + \epsilon$$

Table 4.7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.386 ^a	.149	.144	.93609	.435

a. Predictors: (Constant), AUTOMATED TELLER MACHINE (ATM)

b. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

Table 4.22 provides the *R* and *R*² values. The *R* value represents the simple correlation and the value is 0.386^a which indicates a weak degree of correlation. The *R*² value indicates that 14.9% of the total variation in the dependent variable, ‘Cashless Policy Implementation’ can be explained by the independent variable, ‘Automation Teller Machine ‘service. The Durbin-Watson “d” = 0.435, is between the two critical values of 1.5 < d < 2.5 and therefore we can assume that there is no first order linear auto-correlation in the data. Hence the model is of absolute good fit.

Where:

Y – Dependent variable

X – Independent (explanatory) variable

a – Intercept

b – Slope

ε – Residual (error)

Decision Rule

If the probability value (PV) in the coefficient table is less than 0.05 alpha level, we Reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternate hypotheses of significant relationship. If the probability value (PV) is greater than 0.05 alpha levels, we accept the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

Hypotheses 1-4 are thus analysed below.

H0₁ = Automated Teller Machines (ATM) has no effect on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

Table 4.8: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.250	1	27.250	31.098	.000 ^b
	Residual	155.974	178	.876		
	Total	183.224	179			

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

b. Predictors: (Constant), AUTOMATED TELLER MACHINE (ATM)

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The probability value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship was significant in determining the effect of Automated Teller Machines (ATM) on the implementation of cashless policy by Zenith Bank. The F calculated at 5 percent level of significance was 31.098 which is greater than the F critical (value = 2.4472), this shows that the overall model was significant.

Table 4.9: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	1.199	.178		6.722	.000
	AUTOMATED TELLER MACHINE (ATM)	.342	.061	.386	5.577	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The regression result in table 4.24 shows a model constant (a) value of 1.199 and ATM value of 0.342, indicating that, for every one percent increase in ATM service, the dependent variable 'cashless policy implementation' will rise by 34%. T-value produced 5.577, is significant at P value (.000), which is less than the chosen alpha of α (0.05). Thus, hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that a significant relationship exists between ATM service and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Bank.

H₀₂ = Electronic fund transfer does not affect the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Bank.

Table 4.10: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.395 ^a	.159	.144	.93617	.443

a. Predictors: (Constant), ELECTRONIC FUND TRANSFER

b. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

Table 4.25 provides the R and R^2 values. The R value represents the simple correlation and is 0.395^a which indicates a weak degree of correlation. The R^2 value indicates that 15.9% of the total variation in the dependent variable, 'Cashless Policy Implementation' can be explained by the independent variable, 'Electronic Fund Transfer'. The Durbin-Watson "d" = 0.443, is between the two critical values of $1.5 < d < 2.5$ and therefore we can assume that there is no first order linear auto-correlation in the data. Hence the model is of absolute good fit.

Table 4.11: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.222	1	27.222	32.060	.000 ^b
	Residual	156.003	178	.876		
	Total	183.224	179			

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

b. Predictors: (Constant), ELECTRONIC FUND TRANSFER

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The probability value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship was significant in determining how Electronic Fund Transfer affects the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks. The F calculated at 5 percent level of significance was 32.060 which is greater than the F critical (value = 2.4472), this shows that the overall model was significant.

Table 4.12: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	1.192	.180		6.632	.000
	ELECTRONIC FUND TRANSFER	.337	.061	.385	5.573	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The regression result in table 4.27 shows a model constant (a) value of 1.192 and Electronic Fund Transfer value of 0.337, indicating that, for every one percent increase in Electronic Fund Transfer service, the dependent variable 'cashless policy implementation' will rise by 33%. T-value produced 5.573, is significant at P value (.000), which is less than the chosen alpha of α (0.05). Thus, hypothesis two is rejected. This implies that a significant relationship exists between Electronic Fund Transfer service and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Banks.

H₀₃ = Mobile Banking has no significant impact on the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

Table 4.13: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	of Durbin-Watson
1	.389 ^a	.151	.147	.93458	.435

a. Predictors: (Constant), MOBILE BANKING

b. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY INPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

Table 4.28 provides the *R* and *R*² values. The *R* value is 0.389^a which indicates a weak degree of correlation. The *R*² value indicates that 15.1% of the total variation in the dependent variable, 'Cashless Policy Implementation' can be explained by the independent variable, 'Mobile Banking' which is however, small. The Durbin-Watson "d" = 0.435, is between the two critical values of 1.5 < d < 2.5 and therefore we can assume that there is no first order linear auto-correlation in the data. Hence the model is of absolute good fit.

Table 4.14: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.752	1	27.752	31.774	.000 ^b
	Residual	155.472	178	.873		
	Total	183.224	179			

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY INPLEMENTATION

b. Predictors: (Constant), MOBILE BANKING

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The probability value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship was significant in determining how Mobile Banking affects the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Bank. The *F* calculated at 5 percent level of significance was 31.774 which is greater than the *F* critical (value = 2.4472), this shows that the overall model was significant.

Table 4.15: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	1.168	.182		6.424	.000
	MOBILE BANKING	.360	.064	.389	5.637	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY INPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The regression result in table 4.30 shows a model constant (a) value of 1.168 and Mobile Banking value of 0.360, indicating that, for every one percent increase in Mobile Banking service, the dependent variable ‘cashless policy implementation’ will rise by 36%. T-value produced 5.637, is significant at P value (.000), which is less than the chosen alpha of α (0.05). Thus, hypothesis three is rejected. This implies that a significant relationship exists between Mobile Banking and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Bank.

H₀₄= Point of Sale (POS) operations does not significantly affect the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Banks.

Table 4.16: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.380 ^a	.145	.140	.93838	.434

a. Predictors: (Constant), POINT OF SALE (POS)

b. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

Table 4.31 provides the *R* and *R*² values. The *R* value represents the simple correlation and is 0.380^a which indicates a weak degree of correlation. The *R*² value indicates that 14.5% of the total variation in the dependent variable, ‘Cashless Policy Implementation’ can be explained by the independent variable, ‘Point of Sale’ which is however, small. The Durbin-Watson “d” = 0.434, is between the two critical values of 1.5 < d < 2.5 and therefore we can assume that there is no first order linear autocorrelation in the data. Hence the model is of absolute good fit.

Table 4.17: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26.485	1	26.485	30.078	.000 ^b
	Residual	156.739	178	.881		
	Total	183.224	179			

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

b. Predictors: (Constant), POINT OF SALE (POS)

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The probability value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship was significant in determining how Point of Sale affects the implementation of cashless policy by Deposit Money Bank. The F calculated at 5 percent level of significance was 30.078 which is greater than the F critical (value = 2.4472), this shows that the overall model was significant.

Table 4.18: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	

1	(Constant)	1.237	.175		7.084	.000
	POINT OF SALE (POS)	.309	.056	.380	5.484	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CASHLESS POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The regression result in table 4.33 shows a model constant (a) value of 1.237 and POS value of 0.309, indicating that, for every one percent increase in POS service, the dependent variable 'cashless policy implementation' will rise by 30%. T-value produced 5.484, is significant at P value (.000), which is less than the chosen alpha of α (0.05). Thus, hypothesis four is rejected. This result shows that a significant relationship exists between Point of Sale (POS) service and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Bank.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis of data, the following findings were made:

1. That a significant relationship exists between Automated Teller Machine (ATM) service and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Bank.
2. That a significant relationship exists between Electronic Fund Transfer service and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Banks.
3. That a significant relationship exists between Mobile Banking and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Bank.
4. And that a significant relationship exists between Point of Sale (POS) service and cashless policy implementation by Deposit Money Bank.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the study recommends that for electronic banking to be effective and realize its needed objectives, all Deposit Money Banks should:

1. Ensure a 24/7 uninterrupted internet services for all their operations to encourage mobile banking.
2. Adequately train and periodically retrain its personnel ease and encourage customers' patronage for electronic money transfer.
3. Provide Automated Teller Machines (ATM) in all parts of the country to expand customers' access to the machines.
4. Provide Point on Sale machines to customers at zero-cost to encourage use of the machines.

Research Gaps

The gaps for this study include that no study has been carried out on the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to realize the implementation of the cashless policy by the Central Bank of Nigeria with Abuja as case study. The Federal Capital Territory Abuja is the seat of political and economic power of the country with an increasing population. It should therefore be a point of reference for the implementation of the cashless policy by the Central Bank of Nigeria. Secondly, the studies reviewed did not identify the strategic importance of availability of Internet connectivity in the operations Electronic Banking methods.

Contribution to knowledge

This study has exposed the neglect by Deposit Money Banks on the importance of satisfying customers banking needs in Abuja so as to willing patronize electronic banking system. Other studies can be executed in other parts of the country whose needs are peculiar to their geographical locations.

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